

MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

Orinboev Khurshida Khairullayevna

basic doctoral student at NamDU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17222049>

Annotation. The use of the Uzbek language in the field is important for all areas. In particular, to ensure full and proper use of the state language in all spheres of public life of our country; to ensure the perfect acquisition of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the field in accordance with the norms and rules of written and oral Uzbek and to express personal attitudes towards them in accordance with the literary norms of the Uzbek language.

Keywords: mobile learning, digital technologies, innovation in the educational process, e-learning platforms, mobile applications, interactive learning, digitalization of the educational process, online educational resources, student engagement, educational effectiveness

As our country ranks among the developed countries, it is important, first of all, to cherish our national language, which is the pride of the nation, and its fate, like the fate of the Motherland. In this regard, each of us must understand our responsibility. In the process of moving towards the education and upbringing of the future generation, the main task is to solve the problems of accelerating the education of the state language among the population, increase the effectiveness of education, and enrich the traditional education system with advanced pedagogical technologies. Today, the prestige of our native language in the life of our people and on the international stage is growing.

The reforms of the Head of our state aimed at raising our young people in the spirit of love and pride for the Motherland, loyalty to national traditions and values, worthy successors to the rich heritage of our great ancestors, and widely promoting the concept of the "State Language" are showing their results every day. Serious and effective work is being carried out in this regard. In this regard, in order to ensure the full introduction of the State Language, a number of tasks were set in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5850 dated October 2, 2019 "On measures to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language."

In order to preserve and develop the languages of nations and ethnic groups in Uzbekistan, create conditions for learning the Uzbek language as the state language, determine the strategic goals, priority areas and tasks of the development of the Uzbek language and language policy, as well as future stages, the Concept for the Development of the Uzbek Language and Improvement of Language Policy in 2020-2030, the Implementation Program for 2020-2022, and the main directions for the development of the Uzbek language and improvement of language policy in 2020-2030 were approved by the Decree of

the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6084 “On Measures for the Further Development of the Uzbek Language and Improvement of Language Policy in Our Country” adopted on October 20, 2020.

On April 10, 2020, the Head of State signed the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Establishing the Day of the Uzbek Language Holiday”, and October 21 was designated as the “Day of the Uzbek Language Holiday”.

Based on the tasks set out in the “Program of measures for 2020-2030 to expand and develop the use of the Uzbek language as the state language, support scientific research, and improve teaching methods” of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the end of 2019, teaching of the Uzbek language and literature was established in all non-philological universities.

The idea of fully reflecting the theoretical, practical, creative aspects of the Uzbek language learning process for higher education students and enriching it with innovative technologies was not left out. This will help students to master the subject conveniently and easily. It will create conditions for users to work on themselves. It is intended to accelerate the process of learning the Uzbek language by changing the principles, content and methods of teaching through the Uzbek language in higher education, to deepen and improve the knowledge students have acquired in high school, academic lyceums and vocational colleges, to form speech skills related to using the rich possibilities of the Uzbek language in their specialty, and to learn to express their thoughts correctly, clearly and logically. With this in mind, the educational and methodological complex was created based on the communicative principle aimed at the formation of speech skills.

The use of mobile learning technologies in teaching the Uzbek language allows making lessons interesting, interactive and effective. Mobile learning enriches the lesson process with innovative methods and develops students' independent learning and language skills. The methods of introducing mobile learning into Uzbek language lessons include the following:

- Uzbek language dictionary applications (Uzbek-Russian, Uzbek-English);
- Language learning platforms (Duoling, uzbeklangua);
- Interactive tests and exercises (Quiz test, Kahoot, Google Forms)

Uzbek language lessons on YouTube (educational channels), podcasts and audio books - students can develop listening and comprehension skills by using dictionary applications to memorize new words, write without spelling errors, and reinforce grammar rules through interactive tests, using video lessons and podcasts.

When used in lessons, teachers can watch the recommended video lessons and conduct discussion lessons with students.

The implementation of mobile educational technologies in Uzbek language lessons is an integral part of the modern educational process, making the learning process more interactive, effective and convenient for students.

The results of the study show that the use of mobile applications and digital platforms develops students' independent learning skills and increases their activity in the language learning process. In addition, this approach ensures the flexibility of the learning process and allows for the widespread introduction of innovative methods that meet modern educational standards. Thus, the use of mobile technologies in Uzbek language education is one of the promising areas of digital education, and it is advisable to implement it on a large scale.

Reference:

1. Trigwell K. & Prosser M. Improving the quality of student learning: the influence of learning context and student approaches to learning on learning outcomes. *Higher Education*. 1991. – 22(3). – P. 251-266.
2. Biggs J.B., & Tang C. *Teaching for quality learning at university*. Maidenhead, UK: Open University, 2011.
3. Çetin B. & İlhan M. SOLO taksonomisi. In E. Bingölbali, S. Arslan, & İ.Ö. Zembat (Ed.), *Matematik eğitiminde teoriler*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi. 2016. – pp. 861-879.
4. Bloom B.S., Engelhart M.D., Furst E.J., Hill W.H. & Krathwohl D. *Taxonomy of educational objectives: the cognitive domain* (New York, David McKay Co.). 1956.
5. Barrett S. Bloom's Taxonomy, Educational Objectives, Outcomes, and our Friends from ABET – An Engineering Case Study. 2009.
6. Anderson, L.W., & Krathwohl, D.R. *A taxonomy for learning teaching and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. New York: Longman. 2001.
7. Krathwohl D.R. A revision of Bloom's taxonomy: an overview. *Journal of theory into practice*. 2002. – vol. 41, issue 4, pp. 212-218.
8. Ломов Б.Ф. *Методологические и теоретические проблемы психологии*. – М., 1984. – 444 с.
9. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati: R harfi. – T.: "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi", 2006. – 380 b.
10. Хорошавина Г.Д. Коммуникативная деятельность как детерминанта высшего профессионального образования: Дис д-ра пед. наук / М., 2003. – 189-190 с.